

CHEMICAL SCIENCES

MIXTURE BASED ON POLYLACTIC ACID WITH EPOXY RESIN IN THE PRESENCE OF CHITOSAN

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Abstract

In this study, modified PLA was created by melting polylactic acid after combining it with epoxy resin without the need of a hardener. During melt mixing, chitosan and epoxy resin were added to PLA. Epoxidized natural rubber was melt-blended with polylactic acid and chitosan. A softening test was used to observe the thermal characteristics. The crystallinity and softening point were raised throughout the annealing process. The annealing procedure enhanced the mixture's shape and thermal characteristics while this reaction improved the mechanical properties.

Keywords: epoxy resin, chitosan, naturals, polylactic acid

Introduction

Nearly all insulating components of electrical machines, apparatus, and cable products contain polymers as significant constituents. They are also frequently used to shield insulation from abrasive conditions and mechanical stress. Electrical equipment with high technical and economical features and higher operational reliability can be produced using polymers. [1,2]

There are already up to 70 known directions for the practical application of polylactide, which is the subject of research in more than 15 countries. The following instructions are the most crucial of these. As thickening and structure-forming ingredients required for the production of dietary food products used to remove radionuclides from the body; as simple and multi-component emulsions, additives, and as additives in the production of beer, juice, and wine; as a preservative as well as flavor and odor enhancers, etc. Polylactic acid's bactericidal properties enable the creation of films for the storage of various kinds of food goods. [3,4]. The polylactic films that are affixed to fruits and vegetables including apples, oranges, strawberries, tomatoes, and peppers have more well-known defensive qualities. Fruits and vegetables still possess certain immunological and metabolic processes because they behave like living things even after being cut off from the mother plant. In addition to serving as a microbiological filter on the surface of fruits and vegetables, homogeneous, flexible, non-crackable polylactic films also control the composition of gases on the surface and in the layers of tissues. The activity and kind of respiration are thus impacted by these coatings, which also aid in extending the shelf life of the plant material. In addition, pathogens that affect tomatoes and peppers undergo some morphological changes as a result of the polylactic coating. The biological value of food products is enhanced by the presence of polylactic acid. Additionally, the term "polylactic" describes dietary fibers that the body does not digest and that, in the stomach's acidic

environment, form a viscous solution. The efficiency of medical compounds that are hard to digest is increased and prolonged by polylactic acid. Additionally, it is used to treat other diseases, prevent cardiovascular disease, treat polylactic periodontosis, and treat dental caries. It is also commonly utilized in the creation of shampoos, gels, moisturizers, foundation powders, toothpastes, emollients for hair and face care, and polylactic cosmetics as a moisturizer and emulsifier. In polylactic agriculture, there are biostimulants that increase vegetable productivity by 25–40%, substances that prevent stem and root rot and rust, a special coating that extends plant storage time, and food additives that boost animals' resistance to infectious diseases and their caloric value. removing protein, oil, fat, and other contaminants from waste water in the fields of biotechnology and ecology; Furthermore, the production of detergents, the sorption of radioactive materials and heavy metals, and the immobilization of enzymes all use polylactic acid. [5] Recently, polylactic has gotten a lot of interest since it is a natural material with great biocompatibility, biodegradability, good adhesion, and non-toxic qualities.

Experimental part

Polylactic acid and epoxy resin were melt-mixed in a specialized mill at 130C for 15 minutes to ensure suitability and reactive ability. After that, 5% epoxy resin was melt infused into the mixture. After that, chitosan was combined with epoxy and polylactic acid in a melt after being dissolved in distilled water with 3% (w/v) lactic acid. After being pressed into sheets by being heated to 160C for thirty seconds, the samples were washed in cool water. The samples were heated to a high temperature and annealed for 120 minutes.

Polylactic acid and epoxy resin blends in various ratios have been made and tested. Due to the high temperature of the operation, the mixture's crystallinity in-

creased as annealing time was extended. The 120-minute annealing process increased the thermal stability of the mixture.

While the epoxy groups of the epoxy resin reacted with the -NH groups of the dissolved chitosan, it was found that the epoxy groups of the epoxy resin reacted with the -COOH of polylactic acid. While annealing the mixtures at 80 °C improved their morphology, these reactions improved the mixtures' mechanical and thermal properties. Agricultural practices can benefit from the use of a blend with improved properties.

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